

RIDDLES AS EXAMPLES OF ORAL FOLK LITERATURE

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Abstract. This article discusses riddles that have played an important role in folk oral literature. Riddles are usually questions and tasks in a poetic or prose structure, based on finding a deliberately hidden feature, form, behavior, state and function of an object or event by comparing it with another object or event, and are called riddles, riddles and first-class terms.

Keywords: riddles, genre, folklore, rhyming, dynamism, approach, concept.

Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада халқ оғзаки адабиётида муҳим ўрин тутган топшимоқлар ҳақида гап кетади. Топшимоқлар одатда, нарса ёки ҳодисаларнинг атайлаб яширинган белгиси, шакли, хатти-ҳаракати, ҳолати ва вазифасини бошқа нарса ёки ҳодисаларга қиёслаш асосида топшига асосланган шеърӣй ёки насрий тузилишидаги савол ва топшириқлар ҳисобланади ва улар халқлар ўртасида топшимоқ, жумбоқ, топ-топ атамалари билан юритилади.

Калит сўзлар: топшимоқлар, жумбоқлар, жанр, халқ оғзаки ижоди, қофия, динамизм, ёндашув, тушунчалар.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются загадки, сыгравшие важную роль в народной устной литературе. Загадки обычно представляют собой вопросы и задания в стихотворной или прозаической структуре, основанные на нахождении заведомо скрытого признака, формы, поведения, состояния и функции предмета или события путем сравнения его с другим предметом или событием, и у народов их называют терминами топшимоқ, жумбоқ, топ-топ.

Ключевые слова: загадки, жанр, фольклор, рифмовка, динамичность, подход, концепты.

It is no secret that riddles are usually popular in the culture of all peoples, in general, among the representatives of all nations, and they have always been used in the oral discourse of the people, the nation. That is why riddles are passed down from generation to generation, they live among the people and are inherited, - it is no exaggeration to say. The narration of the riddles also varies from region to region.

According to foreign sources, the origin of the riddles is not clear, and some research suggests that the former were given in Sanskrit, in biblical passages, and in oral tradition stories that became legends. Its birth and development also depend on a person's curiosity and curiosity to know more. On the other hand, some studies have shown that the riddles originated in China, especially in Xang-Cheu during the Sunga Dynasty. A group of men dressed in the same way appeared on the streets, offering money to the public in exchange for answering riddles they posed. As for the etymological origin, the word riddle is derived from the Latin, which consists of a prefix, which means advertising - "correct" and the root divinus - belonging to God [1,12].

As for the properties of riddles, when adding or combining hidden or partial keywords in a text, it consists of speeches that evoke the imagination of the recipient and find a solution until meaning is formed.

Riddles can usually take two different forms. The first is puzzles, in which words that are mostly metaphorical or figurative mean - konundra - a language that requires careful thinking and the meaning of the questions that affect the answer to that question. [1, 20].

Elly Kongas Maranda made such remarks. They argue that puzzles, whereas legends serve to encode and establish social norms, “define puzzles to play with conceptual boundaries and to gain intellectual pleasure in showing that they are not visibly unstable,” he explained. Although there is no known author of riddles in general, they are a folk oral genre that is passed down from nation to nation, and one of the characteristic features of other folk oral genres is that they teach man to think, reason, and come to a solution by distraction. Moreover, one of the main features of riddles is that it sharpens the human brain and helps to create new thoughts, ideas [1, 89].

Now let's look at the definition of the word "riddle" in the Uzbek dictionary: 1. In the riddle game: a short description of what is to be found, an event and a symbol, represented by analogies; puzzle-Children asked Nuri. Nuri had to tell a few riddles, not a fairy tale. But without saying a word, the children found out. (Oybek. Selected works) [2, 532].

2. Portable rarely used: Something mysterious that is difficult to understand; puzzle, problem. Your words sound like a riddle. (S.Siyoev, Light). Life also sometimes seems like a riddle. You know that your destiny will be decided soon, but you will not find what will happen (O. Hoshimov, Listen to your heart).

Typically, riddles are designed to confuse the options offered in order to divert the person to the other side of the game and complicate the solution the interlocutor is finding. It can be given multiple answers, the answer itself will be hidden in the text being given.

While riddles can be used to entertain children, they can also be used in education systems to educate children about concepts and meanings that are part of everyday life, and on the other hand, bringing children together in groups can further enhance popular culture.

The riddles of many countries, if we pay attention, we see that they are similar to each other. In our opinion, the riddles are told by one person, and the representatives of different peoples convey them to their people in their own interpretations, and then these riddles are rhymed and become a national myth of this people. [3, 125].

In the texts of the riddles, the art of metaphor was used as a means of solving a riddle, such as foal, moon, star, lamb, wolf, leopard. Importantly, the riddles in fairy tales and epics played a key role in their creation even when the riddles later began to live as a separate genre. In particular, what must be found for the creation of any riddle is that the properties of the objects were the leading informative factor [3, 165]. As evidence of our opinion, we also found it appropriate to cite examples from fairy tales. The title of the enigmatic tale is as follows:

The answer to Khurayim's question.

At the end of his life, a king named Sultankhan wanted to marry a girl named Khurayim. The sultan sent a suitor/matchmaker to Khurayim. Khurayim asked the following things for exchange:

Ўнта улоқ, (Ten kids)
Ўттизта йўлбарс, (Thirty tigers)
Қирқта тулки, (Forty foxes)
Элликта нухта, (Fifty points)
Олтмишта ахта, (Sixty axes)
Етмишта саргалдоқ, (Seventy yellow orioles)
Саксонта чақалок, (Eighty babies)
Тўқсонта тумалоқ, (Ninety rounds)
Юзта жумалоқ (Hundred rounds)

and asked him to deduce the meaning of that word. The king, after

thinking, said that Khurayim is smart. He said that the meaning of the riddle is related to one's life. The man answered:

Ўнда улоқдай бўлади,
Ўттизда йўлбарсдай бўлади,
Қирқда тулкидай бўлади,
Эллиқда нухталанган отдай ақли расо бўлади,
Олтмишда ахталанган отдай қайтиб қолади.
Етмишда сарғолдоқдай тилда бору дилда ҳеч нарса бўлмайди,
Саксонда гўдак боладай бўлиб қолади,
Тўқсонда уйдан чикмай думалоқ бўлади,

After the king answered Khurayim's question, Khurayim got married and had a son named Rustamkhan.

The riddles provide information about the shape, size, color, function, and similar properties of the object to be found, but these symbols are associated with something else using the art of metaphor.

But the severity of the problem is that we cannot determine in which direction to think using the definition given in some puzzles.

As a conclusion we can say that the role of riddles today is invaluable, as the riddles sharpen the minds of the rising generation.

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